

Sum of Summations of Annamalai's Binomial Expansions

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Abstract: This paper presents a theorem based on the summation of Annamalai's binomial expansions with the binomial coefficient and binomial identity. This theorem is a sort of methodological advance that will help to the researchers who are working in computational science, computation, cryptography, combinatorics, discrete mathematics and theoretical computer science.

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1. Introduction

Computational science is a rapidly growing multi-and inter-disciplinary area where science, engineering, mathematics, and collaboration uses advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real life problems. In this article, we provide the computation/summation of Annamalai's binomial coefficients and its theorem with detailed proofs. The results of Annamalai's binomial coefficients and identities [1- 6] are useful to solve the scientific problems in computational science.

For basic understanding, the traditional coefficient and optimized coefficient are given below:

Traditional coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N \cup \{0\}$ & $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized coefficient: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \text{ \& } V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Summations of Binomial Coefficients

Theorem: $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n$, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{1}{0!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)}{1!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(1+2)}{2!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} + \dots \\ & \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)\dots(i+n-1)}{(n-1)!} = \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)\dots(i+n)}{n!}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: The theorem is provided using the following Annamalai's binomial identity [1 - 6].

Annamalai's binomial identity is that $V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n \dots + V_{r-1}^n + V_r^n = \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1}$.

Let us write the binomial expansions separately for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$ to prove the theorem. Accordingly, we can revise the binomial identity as follows:

$$V_0^{n-1} + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-1} + V_3^{n-1} \dots + V_{r-1}^{n-1} + V_r^{n-1} = \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = V_r^n.$$

For $n = 0$, $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 = V_0^0 + V_1^0 + V_2^0 + \dots + V_r^0 = \frac{r+1}{1!} = V_r^1$ ($\because V_n^0 = V_0^n = V_0^0 = 1$).

For $n = 1$, $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + \frac{r+1}{1!} = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)}{2!} = V_r^2$.

For $n = 2$, $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 = 1 + 3 + 6 + \dots + \frac{(r+1)(r+2)}{2!} = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)}{3!} = V_r^3$.

For $n = 3$, $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 = \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)(r+4)}{4!} = V_r^4$

For $n = 4$, $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^4 = \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)(i+4)}{4!} = \frac{(r+1)(r+2) \dots (r+5)}{5!} = V_r^5$.

Similarly, we can continue this process upto $n - 1$, that is,

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3) \dots (i+n-1)}{(n-1)!} = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3) \dots (r+n)}{n!} = V_r^n.$$

By adding to both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} = \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^n, \quad \text{that is,}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{1}{0!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)}{1!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(1+2)}{2!} + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} + \dots \\ & \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3) \dots (i+n-1)}{(n-1)!} = \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3) \dots (i+n)}{n!}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem based on the summation of Annamalai's binomial expansions has been proved by using the Annamalai's binomial coefficients and application [7]. This is a sort of methodological advance that will help to the researchers who are working in computational science, computation, cryptography, combinatorics, discrete mathematics and theoretical computer science.

References

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